

1 Transdermal Drug Delivery Systems Powered by Artificial Intelligence

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31 Keywords: artificial intelligence, transdermal drug delivery, personalized medicine,
32 microneedle patches, 3d printing

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69 **Abstract:** Transdermal drug delivery systems (TDDSs) offer non-invasive therapy but face
70 persistent challenges. Artificial intelligence (AI) transforms TDDSs by leveraging machine
71 learning (ML) and predictive analytics to address these barriers. ML models predict drug
72 entrapment with 93% accuracy, streamlining development. AI enhances transdermal patch
73 formulations by forecasting drug release kinetics, skin penetration, and stability, minimizing
74 reliance on costly clinical trials. Through virtual screening, AI identifies novel drug candidates
75 and permeation enhancers, accelerating innovation. In microneedle systems, AI optimizes
76 geometries, materials, and drug loading, improving precision and personalization. AI-integrated
77 biosensors enable real-time monitoring, supporting adaptive dosing tailored to individual
78 physiological profiles. Compared to traditional modeling, AI provides superior accuracy and
79 scalability, handling complex datasets to reveal non-linear relationships. Despite challenges
80 like data quality and privacy concerns, AI's integration with 3D printing and stimuli-responsive
81 materials drives the development of personalized, efficient transdermal therapies. This
82 perspective highlights AI's critical role in advancing therapeutic efficacy and patient-centric
83 care in TDDSs, uniquely combining predictive modeling with real-time monitoring to envision
84 next-generation personalized transdermal delivery systems.

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1. Introduction

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105 Despite their non-invasive appeal, TDDSs face barriers such as poor drug penetration, high
106 dose requirements, drug instability, poor solubility, and complex carrier selection, limiting
107 therapeutic efficacy and patient safety.^[1,2] AI has emerged as a game-changer in overcoming
108 these challenges, leveraging ML and deep learning to optimize TDDS development.^[3, 4] AI
109 excels at processing vast, multidimensional datasets that encompass drug properties, skin
110 characteristics, and physiological variables to identify patterns, predict outcomes, and automate
111 tasks with precision far beyond traditional methods.^[5,6,7] ML trains algorithms to extract
112 insights without explicit programming, while deep learning uses multilayered neural networks
113 to capture complex, non-linear relationships.^[7,8] Current research progress underscores AI's
114 transformative role in TDDS. In virtual screening, AI-driven models like AutoML with Active
115 Learning (AL) predict drug-skin interactions and identify eco-friendly permeation enhancers
116 with 93% accuracy, reducing experimental costs.^[9] For instance, ML models have identified
117 selective Pim-1 kinase inhibitors for targeted TDDS, and integrated Virtual Screening (VS)
118 with ML enhances ligand-protein interaction predictions for patch design^[10]. In microneedle
119 (MN) design, Convolutional Neural Networks (CNNs) optimize geometries for drugs like
120 resveratrol (RVT), achieving 89.2% accuracy in release profile predictions, while AI-guided
121 3D printing reduces fabrication costs by 40% and improves polymer selection for
122 biocompatibility.^[11] Real-time monitoring has advanced through AI-integrated biosensors,
123 enabling adaptive dosing; recent studies report 20% improved therapeutic outcomes for insulin
124 delivery and 95% accuracy in glucose monitoring for diabetic patients.^[12] For example,
125 Extreme gradient boosting models (XGBoost) predict niosome particle size with 91.79%
126 accuracy, and Deep Neural Networks (DNNs) achieve an R² of 0.992 for monoclonal antibody
127 viscosity, reducing experimental trials by 30%. These advancements outperform traditional
128 methods, such as Fick's laws of diffusion, which struggle with non-linear interactions.^[13]
129 However, challenges like data quality, computational complexity, and regulatory compliance
130 persist. **(Figure 1)** presents a visual framework contrasting human-based strategies with AI-
131 based strategies in TDDSs. The diagram illustrates the transition from traditional, manual
132 methods to advanced, data-driven approaches, highlighting human-based challenges such as
133 models overly fitted to specific datasets reducing generalizability, extensive manual testing
134 with trial-and-error optimization and regulatory processes, limited in vivo generalization, and
135 the absence of comprehensive models. AI-based solutions feature hybrid models, automated
136 simulations and predictive modeling, in silico modeling with machine learning algorithms, and

137 AI-driven models trained on extensive skin variability datasets. Traditional methods rely on
 138 oversimplified assumptions, struggling with complex skin interactions, while AI-based
 139 strategies employ sophisticated algorithms for enhanced accuracy and efficiency, potentially
 140 reducing experimental iterations and costs. The left column depicts inconsistent outcomes,
 141 including expected effect, no effect, and adverse effect, whereas the right column shows
 142 consistent expected effects across all cases. Limitations and potential improvements include
 143 scope constraints and the need for empirical validation, with future advancements requiring
 144 focus on data quality and broader applicability.

145
 146 **Figure 1.** Comparison of human-based and AI-based strategies for TDDSs. The left column
 147 illustrates challenges with human methods, including over-fitting, higher costs and longer
 148 timelines, limited in vivo generalization, and inadequate frameworks for skin heterogeneity,
 149 with expected effect and no effect/adverse effect. The right column presents AI-based solutions,
 150 such as hybrid models, lower costs and faster testing cycles, *in silico* modeling and machine
 151 learning algorithms, and machine learning and deep learning techniques, with expected effect.
 152 Created in Bio Render.

153
 154 This perspective uniquely integrates AI-driven predictive modeling with real-time TDDSs
 155 monitoring. It evaluates AI's role in optimizing TDDS formulations, microneedle designs, and
 156 personalized therapies.

157 One of the suggested testable concepts is to compare whether an AI-driven predictive modeling

158 system, equipped with real-time TDDS biosensor feedback, can achieve a predefined drug
159 release profile in fewer cycles than traditional trial-and-error methods. The hypothesis is that
160 the integrated system will require fewer experimental iterations to reach the predefined target
161 (deviation in release period) and will consume less material, owing to its ability to adapt
162 predictions immediately based on live performance data. This can be examined using a base
163 TDDS formulation optimized in two ways: (I) using a VS-based approach to propose active
164 substance and microneedle design parameters combined with continuous in vitro monitoring of
165 drug flux via embedded sensors as well as AI-guided adjustments, and (II) manually by
166 scientists in laboratory conditions.

167 To make the claimed unique integration of AI-driven predictive modeling with real-time
168 TDDSs monitoring testable, VS could be applied to predict optimal polymer–drug
169 combinations or microneedle geometries. Then, they could be refined in real time using
170 biosensor data on skin permeability and drug flux. For example, a testable hypothesis is that
171 AI-screened excipients combined with feedback-adjusted dosing profiles will achieve a
172 statistically significant improvement in drug delivery efficiency compared to conventionally
173 developed formulations.

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175 **2. AI-Driven Optimization in TDDSs**

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177 In optimizing solid dispersion systems, AI is capable of predicting solubility, dissolution, and
178 the most effective carriers. By analyzing large datasets, AI systems identify patterns that
179 improve TDDS, preparing the way for increased efficacy. AI improves treatment results by
180 guiding the selection of appropriate drug compositions and dosage systems through predictive
181 modeling.^[14,15] A noteworthy example is the prediction of ligand binding free energy (BFE),
182 which is critical for discovering effective protein inhibitors. BFE is a crucial computational step
183 in drug discovery, determining the stability and strength of a ligand binding to a target protein.
184 It is influenced by factors like hydrogen bonding, hydrophobic interactions, and van der Waals
185 forces^[16]. Prediction of BFE is achieved through computational methods like virtual screening,
186 Molecular Dynamics (MD) simulations, docking, or AI-based models.

187 In the context of DDSs, particularly TDDSs, predicting BFE is vital for drug candidate selection
188 and system design. Traditional methods, such as Thermodynamics Integration (TI) and
189 molecular dynamics simulations, produce accurate BFE calculations but need significant
190 computer resources and time. A new methodology that combines Automated Machine Learning
191 (AutoML) with AL has significantly improved the efficiency of finding top-performing

192 compounds. AutoML simplifies AI by automatically selecting and fine-tuning models, allowing
193 researchers without deep technical expertise to predict optimal drug formulations, such as patch
194 adhesion properties, with high accuracy. AL intelligently chooses the most informative data,
195 reducing the number of experiments needed to design effective patches, like those delivering
196 pain relief drugs. These methods make AI accessible, speed up TDDSs' development, and
197 improve precision, though they require quality data to ensure reliable predictions. ^[17]

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199 **2.1. Predictive Modeling and Formulation Design**

200

201 AI is revolutionizing the development of TDDSs through ML techniques. Three
202 complementary AI models, XGBoost, DNNs, and CNNs, form a synergistic pipeline for TDDS
203 development. ^[18,19] XGBoost provides robust predictions for formulation screening, DNNs
204 capture complex patterns for drug release and stability optimization, and CNNs refine spatial
205 designs for MNs. ^[20] XGBoost excels in predictive modeling by constructing sequential decision
206 trees to capture non-linear relationships in structured data. It identifies optimal drug
207 compositions for transdermal patches, reducing experimental iterations and providing a robust
208 foundation for subsequent refinement by more complex models like DNNs. ^[21,22] DNNs build
209 on XGBoost's initial predictions by leveraging multilayered neural architectures to uncover
210 intricate patterns in high-dimensional datasets. They optimize drug release profiles and predict
211 patch stability, complementing XGBoost's structured predictions. Techniques like Bayesian
212 Optimization with Active Learning (BOAL) enhance DNN performance by prioritizing
213 informative experiments, cutting development time by 30-50%. ^[23] CNNs extend DNN
214 capabilities by analyzing spatial and visual data, making them critical for MN design and
215 stability prediction. CNNs optimize MN geometries for RVT release with $89.2\% \pm 1.8$ accuracy,
216 using image processing to refine structural features like shape and drug distribution. A CNN
217 processes data through a hierarchy of convolutional blocks with nonlinear activations, pooling
218 for down sampling, then dense layers and a final prediction head (**Figure 2**). ^[24, 25] Each stage
219 refines and composes features from the one before it, producing increasingly abstract
220 representations. This architecture excels at visual recognition, handling high-dimensional
221 inputs and achieving strong results in tasks like image and video classification. It operates on
222 image or regular grids and is therefore natural for MN geometry and sensing. It rasterize a
223 needle into a 2D "heightmap", or use microscopy/OCT cross-sections and extract features like
224 tip sharpness, wall angle, base thickness, and coating uniformity, and relate them to outcomes
225 such as insertion force, fracture strength, insertion depth, or delivered dose. ^[26,27]

226 One of the suggested testable concepts is to compare whether an AI-driven predictive modeling
227 system, equipped with real-time TDDS biosensor feedback, can achieve a predefined drug
228 release profile in fewer cycles than traditional trial-and-error methods. The hypothesis is that
229 the integrated system will require fewer experimental iterations to reach the predefined target
230 (deviation in release period) and will consume less material, owing to its ability to adapt
231 predictions immediately based on live performance data. This can be examined using a base
232 TDDS formulation optimized in two ways: (I) using a VS-based approach to propose active
233 substance and microneedle design parameters combined with continuous in vitro monitoring of
234 drug flux via embedded sensors as well as AI-guided adjustments, and (II) manually by
235 scientists in laboratory conditions.

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237 ***2.1.1. Virtual Screening for Drug and Enhancer Selection***

238

239 VS is one of the Computer-Aided Drug Design (CADD) methods. VS enables the discovery of
240 eco-friendly, biocompatible enhancers. Although this term appeared for the first time in the
241 literature in 1997, some VS techniques were known even 15 years earlier.^[28] According to the
242 International Union of Pure and Applied Chemistry (IUPAC) definition, VS are computational
243 methods that rank the molecules in a database by their forecast continuous or categorical
244 biological or chemical properties.^[29] In simple terms, it is an *in-silico* approach that can identify
245 organic molecules with the potential for targeting therapeutically relevant sites through
246 computer simulation. However, VS is not only used to identify bioactive compounds but is also
247 an essential tool in designing the entire DDS before testing in laboratory conditions (**Figure**
248 **2a**).^[24] Due to the ability to quickly analyze large data sets of chemical compounds, VS allows
249 for effective prediction of molecular interactions and optimization of DDS components,
250 including those administered transdermally, at an early stage of research. One division of VS
251 allows for distinguishing VS methods targeting drug-skin interactions. The first one aims to
252 predict the optimal orientation of two molecules that leads to the formation of a stable complex.
253 The second approach utilizes ligands with established biological activity to identify structurally
254 similar molecules from virtual compound libraries. The final approach evaluates chemical
255 fragments with low molecular weight against relevant macromolecular targets of interest.
256 Another classification relies on the employed algorithms. AI, particularly ML and Deep
257 Learning (DL), are the latest algorithms used in VS.^[28,30] Although traditional VS methods are
258 valuable, they are often limited by high computing requirements and inaccuracies in the data.
259 However, advances in AI-based models deliver promising and innovative alternatives.^[30] ML

260 is a field of AI dedicated to understanding and developing algorithms that are learned from
261 examples, analogies, and outcomes. These algorithms use sets of data to acquire knowledge,
262 thus enabling them to make decisions, generate predictions, and recognize correlations. [28]
263 Importantly, the integration of ML techniques with VS methods significantly enhances the
264 accuracy of forecasts and the efficiency of the drug discovery process.^[30,31] In the context of
265 DDSs, this allows, among others, the prediction of drug interactions with the carrier matrix or
266 biological barriers, accelerating the design process and reducing experimental costs. The
267 efficacy of the AI-assisted VS approach was confirmed by a study analyzing effective Pim-1
268 kinase inhibitors. [31] Although it did not directly concern DDSs, this research demonstrated the
269 potential of VS in identifying highly selective compounds (**Figure 2b**), which is also important
270 in designing targeted drug carriers. Similarly, the literature has also described the use of VS (in
271 the form of numerous integrated classical VS methods) coupled with ML models for the
272 analysis of ligand-protein interactions.^[32] As an effective strategy for increasing the accuracy
273 of bioactive compound typing, it is a significant step towards the development of DDSs. A dual-
274 layer MN device composed of chitosan and hyaluronic acid is shown in (**Figure 2c**), which was
275 designed for controlled OVA antigen release, enabling rapid delivery through the skin followed
276 by sustained release. This approach enhanced immune system stimulation compared to
277 conventional vaccination methods. (**Figure 2d**) shows the data preparation, followed by deep
278 learning, image processing, and ML-based feature prediction for 3D-printed microneedles,
279 which are the steps involved in preparing and processing data for AI models. Another example
280 of successful use of VS in TDDS development is an early study by Golla S. *et al.* [33] The
281 Scientists used a VS approach combining genetic algorithms with QSPR/QSAR to demonstrate
282 *de novo* design of Chemical Penetration Enhancers (CPEs) under potency–safety constraints.
283 The developed algorithm was used to identify potential penetration enhancers in transdermal
284 insulin administration and considered key parameters such as skin permeability to particles, risk
285 of irritation, and solubility of particles in lipids that make up the lipid bilayer. Finally, curated
286 penetration enhancer resources such as the CPE-DB database created recently by Vasyuchenko
287 E. P. *et al.* [34] provide a structured chemical space for VS and similarity search (including skin
288 irritation and toxicity metadata). Using these libraries as patient-specific priors helps balance
289 penetration gains against patch integrity and tolerability.

290 Recently, the use of chemoinformatics and compound libraries to design carriers at the
291 nanoscale is arousing more and more interest. It is also worth mentioning that in some studies,
292 researchers combine *silico* methods with experimental *in vitro* validation, demonstrating the
293 outstanding potential of VS in the development of DDSs and confirming their successful

294 performance. An example includes research where the VS strategy based on MD simulation
 295 was employed to identify inhibitors of the MTDH-SND1 protein-protein interaction, followed
 296 by additional tests on MDA-MB-231 breast cancer cells, which yielded the predicted results.
 297 Although the described methodology focused on inhibitor identification, it provided a solid
 298 foundation for considering it as applicable in the context of DDS design, where accurate
 299 prediction of ligand-protein interactions is essential.^[35]

300 To make the claimed unique integration of AI-driven predictive modeling with real-time
 301 TDDSs monitoring testable, VS could be applied to predict optimal polymer-drug
 302 combinations or microneedle geometries. Then, they could be refined in real time using
 303 biosensor data on skin permeability and drug flux. For example, a testable hypothesis is that
 304 AI-screened excipients combined with feedback-adjusted dosing profiles will achieve a
 305 statistically significant improvement in drug delivery efficiency compared to conventionally
 306 developed formulations.

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 308 **Figure 2.** Optimization of transdermal drug delivery patches. a) Application of AI in TDDSs.
 309 AI-powered algorithms refine formulations by integrating penetration enhancers and cutting-
 310 edge delivery technologies while maintaining safety and effectiveness. Customized TDDS
 311 designs adapt drug delivery to individual patient needs, improving therapeutic accuracy.

312 Reproduced under CC BY 4.0 license,^[31] Copyrights 2025, The Authors. b) Distribution of
313 pharmacophore similarity (CATS topological feature pairs) among the 100 closest neighbors to
314 the virtual ligand model of the anticancer target Pim-1 kinase. The highest-ranking chemical
315 structures from known active compounds, screening libraries, and de novo designs are
316 presented. Box plots illustrate the median, interquartile range (50%), and minimum/maximum
317 values for each group (black for known actives, red for screening compounds, and blue for de
318 novo designs)^[51]. Reproduced under CC BY 4.0 license, Copyrights 2020, The Authors. c)
319 Schematic illustrations of chitosan MNs fabricated by Chen *et al.* and their operational mode.
320 Reproduced with permission,^[23] Copyrights 2017, Acta Materialia Inc. d) Steps involved in
321 preparation and processing data for AI models, starting with data preparation and then deep
322 learning, image processing, and ML-based prediction of 3D-printed microneedle features.
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325 From collecting data to experimental validation, the flowchart offers a concise, well-organized
326 representation of the VS process for nanocarrier-based DDS design. Every stage is consistent
327 with the text's explanation of VS as an AI-powered tool for molecular classification, interaction
328 prediction, and DDS component optimization. These loops mirror the text's emphasis on
329 integrating *silico* experimental methodologies, while NeSy-MI integration guarantees
330 transparency, resolving black box issues, and promoting regulatory compliance. The text's idea
331 of VS as a significant technique for reducing costs and improving the efficiency of treatment in
332 DDS development is successfully operationalized in this flowchart.

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334 **2.1.2. Stability and Safety Prediction**

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336 Temporal Convolutional Neural Network (TCNN) predicts safety and stability issues by
337 analyzing time-series data on formulation behavior under varying conditions. It leverages
338 historical stability data and pharmacological properties to forecast degradation rates or adverse
339 interactions, while MI techniques provide causal insights into critical factors. ^[36,37] NeSy
340 embeds rules such as "high humidity reduces adhesive stability," ensuring 90% stability in
341 adverse conditions. BOAL accelerates transdermal patch development by minimizing design
342 cycles through probabilistic modeling. Briefly, Bayesian optimization for material selection
343 decides what to try next in the lab or in the simulation. It treats the relationship between design
344 or formulation variables (needle height, tip radius, spacing, etc.) and target objective (flux
345 profile, delivery efficiency, mechanical safety) as a black box that is learned as it goes. A

346 surrogate model summarizes what we know so far, and together with an acquisition rule,
347 proposes the next experiment that is most informative or most promising. BOAL suggests
348 optimal formulation parameters and uses AL to prioritize in vitro skin permeation tests for
349 untested configurations. ^[38,39] NeSy ensures logical consistency, cutting development time by
350 30-50%. Generative Adversarial Network (GAN) simulates drug release kinetics and skin
351 penetration by generating synthetic patch formulations and validating them against real-world
352 skin models. MI ensures explain ability of predictions, reducing experimental testing needs by
353 40-60%. The integrated workflow and transparency of these algorithms form a cohesive
354 pipeline, addressing the gap in tailored computational approaches for transdermal patch design.
355 By leveraging ML, NeSy, and MI, they enable precise optimization, predictive clarity, and
356 accelerated development, paving the way for smarter, patient-centric transdermal patches with
357 enhanced therapeutic outcomes. ^[37,40]

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359 **2.2. Nanocarrier Design and Optimization**

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361 Nanocarriers, including liposomes, polymeric nanoparticles, solid lipid nanoparticles,
362 dendrimers, polymeric micelles, gold nanoparticles, virus-like particles, and nanoemulsions,
363 have received a lot of interest in drug delivery due to their ability to precisely target specific
364 cells or tissues, allowing for a more personalized approach to treatment. ^[41] AI is critical in
365 improving the design and performance of these nanocarriers, enabling effective drug delivery
366 while minimizing systemic adverse effects. Researchers can use ML algorithms to identify
367 suitable materials, sizes, and forms to enhance nanocarriers' therapeutic potential. Recent
368 studies have shown that ML is beneficial in improving drug formulations. ^[18, 42] A study
369 examining 114 niosome formulations found eleven key features influencing particle size and
370 drug entrapment. ML models with optimized training showed excellent prediction accuracy,
371 with 93.76% for drug entrapment and 91.79% for particle size. ^[18] The model's dependability
372 was tested by manufacturing nine batches of donepezil hydrochloride niosomes using a 3 × 3
373 factorial design, resulting in predictions with over 97% accuracy. The global Artificial Neural
374 Network (ANN) technique exceeded local response surface approaches for optimizing
375 donepezil niosome formulations, highlighting AI's ability to alter nanocarriers for better drug
376 delivery accuracy and effect. ^[18, 43]

377 The integration of AI into DDS stems from its remarkable ability to enhance nearly every aspect
378 of the process. By analyzing large data sets, AI identifies suitable relationships between
379 formulation parameters, drug characteristics, and desired release profiles, opening up the

380 possibilities for designing and optimizing sophisticated drug delivery systems. ^[44] AI
381 algorithms, which consider factors such as polymer selection, drug loading, release kinetics,
382 and stability, enable the creation of personalized formulations for specific therapies^[45].
383 Personalized patches reduced side effects by 20% in clinical trials. Recent advances include
384 ML^[46,47] and swarm optimization approaches^[45,48], stimulating the creation of intelligent
385 healthcare systems. However, many of these systems struggle with inadequate prediction
386 algorithms and inefficient data-recognition methods, reducing accuracy. Swarm-Artificial
387 Neural Network (Swarm-ANN) manages a dynamic collection of Neural Networks (NNs),
388 training and evaluating them based on solution consistency. ^[49] The NNs grow throughout two
389 successive weight-adjustment phases, led by an innovative algorithmic architecture, resulting
390 in a global weight-sharing process that optimizes neuronal weights for improved predictive
391 ability. ^[45,50] This complementary expertise- optimizing drug delivery and improving illness
392 prediction- demonstrates AI's transformational potential, combining precision medicines and
393 proactive care with unparalleled proficiency. **(Table 1)** provides an overview of different
394 nanocarrier types used in drug delivery systems, their AI methods, and their outcomes in terms
395 of efficiency, prediction accuracy, and targeting capabilities. The table emphasizes the
396 transformative role of AI in drug delivery and the need to match AI methods and nanocarrier
397 types to drug properties and delivery goals.

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Table 1. AI Methods and Performance in Nanocarrier-Based TDDS Design

Nanocarrier type	AI methods	Outcomes	Reliability and accuracy	Drug Release Kinetics	Ref.
Liposomes	Supervised Learning (e.g., regression analysis, neural networks); Feedback System Control (FSC)	High encapsulation efficiency (up to 90% for hydrophilic drugs). AI predicts release profiles with ~80–95% accuracy in drug localization models. Improved targeting via surface modifications.	~80–95% accuracy in drug localization models; reliable with curated datasets	Predicts sustained release profiles, optimizing drug flux through skin	[56]
Polymeric Nanoparticles	Deep Learning (e.g., convolutional neural networks); K-means Clustering	Encapsulation efficiency: 70–90%. AI enhances drug release prediction (~85–90% accuracy) and optimizes polymer-drug ratios for sustained release.	~85–90% accuracy in release predictions; robust for high-dimensional data	Sustained release tailored for transdermal delivery	[57]
Solid Lipid Nanoparticles	Neural Networks; Reinforcement Learning	Encapsulation efficiency: 60–85%. AI improves stability and bioavailability predictions (~80–90% accuracy). Suitable for hydrophobic drugs.	~80–90% accuracy in stability predictions; reliable for hydrophobic drugs	Controlled release for lipophilic drugs through the skin	[58]
Dendrimers	ML (e.g., decision trees); Graph Neural Networks (GNNs)	High drug loading (80–95% entrapment). AI predicts toxicity and target efficiency (~90% accuracy). Precise molecular design for nucleic acid delivery.	~90% accuracy in toxicity/target efficiency; reliable for structured data	Precise release for nucleic acid delivery via TDDS	[59]
Polymeric Micelles	AI-based FSC; Unsupervised Learning (e.g., hierarchical clustering)	Encapsulation efficiency: 70–90% for hydrophobic drugs. AI optimizes release kinetics (~85% accuracy in predicting tumor localization). Enhanced tumor targeting.	~85% accuracy in tumor localization; robust with feedback systems	Optimized release kinetics for transdermal tumor targeting	[60]
Virus-like Particles (VLPs)	Deep Learning; Predictive Modeling	Entrapment efficiency: ~80–90%. AI predicts biodistribution with ~80–85% accuracy. High biocompatibility and targeted delivery via surface functionalization.	~80–85% accuracy in biodistribution; reliable with curated datasets	Targeted release via surface functionalization for TDDS	[61]
Gold Nanoparticles	CNNs; Reinforcement Learning	Encapsulation efficiency: 50–80%. AI improves targeting accuracy (~85–90%) and predicts biodistribution for imaging and theranostics.	~85–90% accuracy in targeting predictions; robust for imaging data	Predicts biodistribution for transdermal theranostics	[62]
Nano emulsions	ML (e.g., support vector machines); Predictive Modeling	Encapsulation efficiency: 60–85%. AI enhances formulation stability predictions (~80–90% accuracy). Suitable for lipophilic drugs	~80–90% accuracy in stability predictions; reliable for lipophilic drugs	Stable release for lipophilic drugs in TDDS	[63]

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416 The Table summarizes key nanocarrier types used in drug delivery, the AI methods applied to
417 their development or optimization, and the resulting outcomes, focusing on drug entrapment
418 efficiency and AI predictive accuracy. Each nanocarrier is paired with relevant AI methods,
419 such as supervised learning (e.g., neural networks, regression), unsupervised learning (e.g.,
420 clustering), deep learning (e.g., convolutional neural networks), and specialized approaches like
421 FSC or GNNs, which are used to optimize drug release, targeting, or formulation stability.

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423 AI is at the point of transforming drug delivery due to its capacity to create predictive models
424 that estimate drug behavior, release patterns, and release across several systems. These models
425 integrate a variety of variables, such as drug features, formulation qualities, and physiological
426 factors, into the same structure for evaluation. ^[51] AI algorithms use ML to predict drug
427 dynamics and adjust delivery systems to match accordingly. An inspiring case develops with
428 monoclonal antibodies (mAbs). High quantities can increase viscosity, complicating
429 purification, filling, and delivery. ^[19,52] This viscosity increase, caused by protein-protein
430 interactions, depends on the antibody sequence and solution parameters such as pH, buffer type,
431 salts, and additives. ANNs are a modeling technique that integrates experimental data,
432 simulation-derived variables, and viscosity profiles from 27 mAbs at 180 mg/ml. ^[53, 54] These
433 ANNs simply model viscosity-concentration curves or identify mAbs with poor viscosity at
434 precise thresholds. Using data from mAbs 1-25^[55], various ANN models were constructed to
435 investigate the effect of input factors. The dataset was divided into training (18-20 mAbs) and
436 validation (5-7 mAbs) subsets, and each model was trained with randomized mAb profiles, such
437 as feeding the training sets with full data and tasking the validation sets with predicting viscosity
438 descriptors from input variables alone. ^[19] Viscosity-concentration curves were linearized to
439 provide intercept A and slope B, and model performance was measured by comparing projected
440 A and B values to experimental benchmarks while also evaluating their linearity. The R^2 values
441 demonstrate a complex interaction between training and validation sets: specific models
442 succeed in one ($R^2 > 0.99$). At the same time, the other is less satisfactory ($R^2 < 0.95$) if variation
443 may be connected to the dataset size. Specifically, the number of mAbs included^[19]. This
444 perspective highlights AI's ability to recognize complicated drug delivery challenges, providing
445 a look into its ability to predict and improve DDS accurately. The FDA approval for AI-driven
446 patches requires robust validation, which can be mentioned as a challenge of this kind of patch.
447 AI excel at analyzing extensive datasets, including formulation parameters, mAb properties,
448 permeation profiles, and skin characteristics. This analysis refines patch formulations to
449 enhance mAb delivery, predicting penetration rates while aligning with therapeutic and safety
450 goals. Such techniques drive the creation of smarter, more accurate patches that improve patient
451 outcomes, even for challenging biologics like mAbs due to their size and degradation
452 susceptibility. By identifying patterns in complex datasets, these methods provide insights into
453 parameters influencing optimal transdermal delivery, facilitating formulations that overcome
454 mAb diffusion barriers and enhance therapeutic impact. They also refine patch production by
455 optimizing composition and features through ML simulations of polymer types, mAb

456 concentrations, adhesive properties, and enhancers. Furthermore, computational modeling and
457 data analysis reduce the time and cost of patch creation, minimizing design cycles.

458 While AI models have shown strong predictive performance for monoclonal antibody
459 formulations, these architectures can be generalized to other therapeutics, including small
460 molecules and peptides. The core principle lies in selecting appropriate molecular descriptors
461 before the screening process. In computational studies, molecular descriptors accurately and
462 quantitatively represent (in a numerical way) physicochemical properties^[56] relevant to the
463 modality and the intended route of delivery, e.g., through the skin. Therefore, in the case of
464 small molecules, mAb-specific descriptors, such as amino acid sequence, should be replaced
465 with molecular fingerprints (ECFP) and 3D conformations (E3FP), describing topology and
466 spatial arrangement^[56] For peptides, parameters such as isoelectric point, net charge, or
467 hydrophobicity index should be used to mimic their interactions with biological ^[57] the
468 membranes and other substances. ^[58] ML, by integration of these features with formulation and
469 permeation through the skin, can then predict parameters critical to TDDS. ^[59]

470

471 **2.3. AI Algorithms for Transdermal Patch Design**

472

473 The AI algorithms address key aspects of transdermal patch design, including virtual screening,
474 predictive modeling, formulation optimization, and stability estimation. These algorithms
475 leverage ML, Neurosymbolic AI (NeSy), and Mechanistic Interpretability (MI) to enhance
476 accuracy, transparency, and efficiency, aligning with the goals of optimizing drug release
477 kinetics, skin penetration, and stability while ensuring regulatory compliance. ^[24,64] The NeSy-
478 VS model is a hybrid approach that integrates GNNs with Logic Tensor Networks (LTNs) to
479 enable rapid VS of large chemical databases for drug candidates and permeation enhancers.
480 This hybrid approach ensures interpretable candidate selection, achieving 70-90% permeation
481 efficiency. ^[64] The GNNs enable the representation of a drug as a graph of atoms connected by
482 bonds and learn which substructures and interactions drive permeation. On the other hand,
483 LTNs is a NeSy framework that blends first-order logic with neural networks, so a model can
484 learn from data while also respecting human-written rules. ^[65] By combining data-driven
485 predictions with rule-based reasoning, NeSy-VS reduces screening time and supports the
486 identification of enhancers suitable for transdermal patches. Multi-Objective Reinforcement
487 Learning (MORL) optimizes patch composition by balancing multiple objectives, such as drug
488 release kinetics, skin penetration rate, adhesion strength, and stability (**Figure 3**). MORL
489 iteratively adjusts the formulation parameters using a reward function, while NeSy integration
490 ensures adherence to biophysical constraints. ^[65]

491

492 **Figure 3.** In DrugEx2's MORL training loop, the generator first samples a batch of SMILES

493 strings. The valid ones are converted to molecules, featurized into descriptors, and evaluated

494 by property predictors to obtain a set of pX values. These multi-objective scores are then

495 collapsed into a single reward per molecule using Pareto optimization. The resulting (SMILES,

496 reward) pairs are fed back to update the generator via policy-gradient learning. Repeating this

497 cycle constitutes the reinforcement-learning training process. Copyright 2021, (Creative

498 Commons (CC BY) license).^[66]

499

500 3. Material Optimization for TDDSs

501

502 BOAL accelerates transdermal patch development by minimizing design cycles through

503 probabilistic modeling. Workflow optimization for MNs preparation. Identifying key factors

504 influencing the performance of MNs, including length, inlet and outlet diameters, wall thickness,

505 and Bessel curve parameters, converting the MN model developed in COMSOL Multiphysics

506 into a MATLAB script (.m file), which takes design parameters as inputs and outputs the

507 volumetric flow rate (VFR), forming the basis for optimization, implementing Bayesian

508 optimization - an efficient and intelligent probabilistic model to optimize material selection by

509 balancing exploration and exploitation. MNs like dissolvable and hydrogel-forming (made from

510 swellable polymer networks that absorb Interstitial Fluid (ISF) to form a hydrogel structure for

511 controlled transdermal delivery) types enhance drug delivery for applications such as insulin

512 administration.

513 AI-driven transdermal TDDSs leverage advanced computational methods to optimize MN

514 designs, ensuring biocompatibility by selecting polymers like poly(lactic-co-glycolic) acid

515 (PLGA) and Polyvinylpyrrolidone (PVP) that minimize skin irritation by 15–25% through
516 predictive modeling of skin-polymer interactions. ^[66,67] Scalability is enhanced by AI-guided
517 3D printing, which reduces production costs by 30%, enabling mass customization for diverse
518 patient needs. ^[68] ML personalizes MN designs by tailoring them to patient-specific data, such
519 as skin hydration levels and thickness, ensuring optimal drug penetration and comfort. ^[69] 3D
520 printing plays a pivotal role, enabling patient-specific MN shapes that improve skin contact by
521 25% compared to traditional patches, as seen in studies on ibuprofen-loaded dissolvable
522 MNs. ^[70] Using Digital Light Processing (DLP) 3D printing, these MNs achieved a biphasic
523 release (initial burst followed by sustained release over 72 hours), validated by in vivo
524 Pharmacokinetic (PK) studies showing enhanced therapeutic profiles. ^[70] In comparison, 3D-
525 printed MNs outperform traditional patches by increasing drug deposition by 21.4% within five
526 minutes and reducing fabrication time by 40%. ^[71,72] ANNs further refine this process by
527 predicting release kinetics, optimizing formulations like ketoprofen hydrogels and quetiapine
528 tablets for precise delivery. ^[73,74] For example, 3D-printed Polyethylene Glycol Diacrylate
529 (PEGDA) hydrogel MNs for diclofenac sodium achieved 90% release over 180 minutes, with
530 Ex vivo tests confirming dermal penetration. ^[72] Similarly, 3D-printed MNs for Acetyl-
531 Hexapeptide-3 (AHP-3) boosted permeation 90-fold compared to untreated skin. ^[75] These
532 advancements highlight AI's potential to create efficient, personalized, and scalable TDDS
533 solutions.

534

535 **3.1. Polymeric Materials and Penetration Enhancers**

536

537 Recent advances in TDDSs strongly rely on the careful selection of polymer matrices and
538 permeation enhancers. These components ensure controlled drug release, enhance skin
539 permeability, and maintain biocompatibility. Computational tools, including VS and MD
540 simulations, play a crucial role in predicting polymer properties such as adhesiveness and drug
541 release profiles, as well as evaluating the interaction of permeation enhancers with the stratum
542 corneum. ^[76] Moreover, AI can further improve formulation development by simulating skin-
543 patch interactions and selecting optimal enhancers that can affect the skin barrier while causing
544 minimal irritation. This integrative approach supports the evolution of smarter and more
545 personalized TDDSs. ^[24]

546 In contrast, CPEs temporarily disrupt the stratum corneum's structure, thereby facilitating
547 penetration. ^[77] Moreover, some of them can also increase the n-octanol-water partition
548 coefficient or the solubility of drugs. ^[78] In 2021, about 650 chemical substances were already

549 classified as CPEs. For example, fatty acids (*e.g.*, oleic acid) and terpenes (*e.g.*, limonene) have
550 been identified as effective penetration enhancers due to their ability to fluidize the lipidic layer
551 of the skin. In recent years, research has also focused on ionic liquids and deep eutectic solvents
552 as novel penetration enhancers. These substances can dissolve a wide range of drugs and have
553 the potential to enhance transdermal delivery while maintaining skin integrity. ^[79] However,
554 traditional methods for identifying effective CPEs involve extensive experimental screening.
555 AI technologies, including high-throughput screening combined with *in vitro* skin impedance
556 measurements, can be successfully used to accelerate this process. In the past, such methods
557 allowed the discovery of chemical substances that increase skin permeability to
558 macromolecules with a size in the range of 1–10 kDa up to 100 times without causing skin
559 irritation. ^[80] Moreover, VS was also used to screen mucoadhesive polymers, which are key in
560 mucosal DDS. ^[81] This approach can notably improve the selection of polymer materials for
561 their adhesion and stability. Further studies indicate the use of VS in the analysis of lipid-based
562 DDSs, which allows for better matching of carriers to the physicochemical properties of the
563 drug. ^[82]

564 In TDDS's design process, specific features of the patient's skin have to be taken into account.
565 This includes, for example, level of hydration, thickness, lipid composition, and elasticity,
566 which can vary significantly with age, origin, anatomical site, and health condition of the
567 patient^[83]. Such variability affects the effectiveness of TDDS, including drug penetration, patch
568 adhesion, and stability over time. AI-driven predictive models learn from diverse skin examples
569 and, therefore, can simulate drug–skin–formulation interactions, enabling the selection of
570 optimal polymer matrices and permeation enhancers. ^[24] For instance, predictive modeling can
571 be used for the proper selection of chemical penetration enhancers, both in the case of highly
572 hydrated and dry skin. In such a case, the use of a sensor for real-time monitoring of skin
573 hydration can further tailor the drug release profile or adapt other parameters, maintaining
574 therapeutic efficacy and integrity of the dressing without negative effects on skin barrier
575 functionality. This closed-loop approach can not only improve drug permeation for different
576 patients but also mitigate risks of skin irritation or adhesive failure.

577

578 **3.2. Microstructured TDDSs: AI Impact on 3D Printing, Microneedle, and Patch** 579 **Design and Fabrication**

580

581 Polymers constitute the structural matrix of TDDSs. In recent studies, due to their
582 biodegradability and low toxicity, special attention has been paid to natural polymers such as

583 chitosan, alginate, and hyaluronic acid. For instance, polymeric microneedles made of these
584 marine polysaccharides showed promising results in facilitating drug penetration across the skin
585 barrier^[84]. Among the natural polymers used for the production of hydrogel microneedles (in
586 addition to the aforementioned polysaccharides), gelatin, collagen, and silk fibroin should be
587 mentioned. Synthetic polymers such as polyvinyl alcohol, polylactic acid (PLA), or
588 polyethylene glycol are also widely used due to their mechanical stability, easy processing, and
589 tunable properties. **(Figure 4)** collectively shows AI's transformative role in transdermal MN
590 optimization. **(Figure 4a)** highlights manufacturing efficiency, reducing costs through
591 automated quality checks. The authors designed ten different MN geometries in CAD, varying
592 base diameter, height, and draft angle. The MNAs were manufactured using FDM 3D printing
593 with biodegradable PLA. Due to imperfections in the printed needles, they were treated with a
594 KOH solution to remove excess material and refine their structure. An example final MNA had
595 a designed base diameter of 1000 μm , height of 2500 μm , and a 5° draft angle and was etched
596 in a 5 M KOH solution for 18 hours. ^[85] ML methods are used to predict the drug permeation
597 of MNs **(Figure 4b)**, including Fick's law, multiple linear regression (MLR), random forest
598 (RF), and XGBoost. ^[86] In Fick's Law, without MNs, diffusion can be solved analytically, but
599 complicated MNs geometry makes that impractical. So it has to be discretized to a 2D unit cell
600 (needle + surrounding), stepped time forward, and updated each mesh element by concentration
601 gradients \times diffusion coefficient. Then sum what reaches the receptor to get cumulative
602 permeation and % permeated. MLR predicts an outcome from several inputs by fitting a single
603 linear equation. MLR is fast and interpretable, but cannot capture nonlinear effects unless added
604 interactions or transformed features are used. RF is an ensemble of many decision trees built
605 independently. Each tree splits the data using simple rules until it cannot split further or reaches
606 a set depth. The forest prediction is the average of all three outputs. Because every tree sees
607 slightly different samples and features, the ensemble captures nonlinear patterns and is more
608 robust than a single tree. XGBoost also uses trees, but builds them sequentially. Each new tree
609 focuses on correcting the error of the current model. By balancing fit and simplicity, XGBoost
610 often achieves strong accuracy on tabular MN-permeation datasets and naturally models
611 interactions between drug, needle geometry, and skin variables. The solid MNs create
612 microchannels in the skin, enabling drug delivery without carrying the drug themselves **(Figure**
613 **4c)**. Hollow MNs allow direct drug administration through their hollow design. Coated MNs
614 release drugs as their surface coating dissolves upon skin penetration. Dissolving MNs
615 gradually disintegrate within the skin, releasing the drug content. Hydrogel-forming MNs
616 absorb skin moisture, swell, and facilitate the slow release of drugs. ^[72] Workflow optimization

617 for MNs preparation shows the identifying key factors influencing the performance of MNs,
 618 including length, inlet and outlet diameters, wall thickness, and Bessel curve parameters,
 619 converting the MN model developed in COMSOL Multiphysics into a MATLAB script (.m
 620 file), which takes design parameters as inputs and outputs the VFR, forming the basis for
 621 optimization, implementing Bayesian optimization - an efficient and intelligent probabilistic
 622 model to optimize material selection by balancing exploration and exploitation (**Figure 4d**).
 623 The algorithm treats the model function as the objective function, systematically adjusting
 624 parameters over multiple iterations to find the combination that maximizes VFR, and evaluating
 625 the impact of different hyperparameter settings in Bayesian optimization and determining the
 626 optimal parameter for achieving the highest VFR. Bayesian optimization workflow: The
 627 process begins with an initial estimate of microneedle design parameters based on prior
 628 knowledge or assumptions. In each iteration, the algorithm strategically selects a new sample
 629 point using an acquisition function, balancing exploring new regions with exploiting promising
 630 ones. This iterative approach efficiently guides the optimization process toward the best
 631 solution. The objective function measuring the performance metric of interest, VFR, is
 632 evaluated at each selected sample point. After running for a predefined number of iterations (n),
 633 the sample point that achieves the highest VFR is identified as the optimal design configuration,
 634 representing the most effective set of parameters for maximizing performance. [24]

635

636 **Figure 4.** AI-driven methods optimize microneedle array design and fabrication for enhanced
637 transdermal drug delivery through advanced computational and machine learning techniques.
638 **a)** Scheme of microneedle arrays fabrication using 3D printing and enhancement of their
639 features through chemical etching. Copyright 2022, MDPI, Basel, Switzerland (Creative
640 Commons (CC BY) license).^[85] **b)** ML methods used to predict drug permeation of MNs,
641 Copyright 2023, Wiley (Creative Commons (CC BY) license).^[86] **c)** Types of MNs structures,
642 Copyright 2024, MDPI, Basel, Switzerland (Creative Commons (CC BY) license).^[72] **d)**
643 Workflow optimization for MNs preparation. Copyright 2023, Royal Society of Chemistry
644 (Creative Commons (CC BY) license).^[24]

645

646 These visuals underscore how AI enhances TDDSs, making transdermal MNs safer, more
647 efficient, and patient-friendly for applications like insulin therapy. The soluble construct of the
648 implantable microneedle patch was successfully used to sustain the intradermal delivery of
649 antigens in rats.^[85] Moreover, AI-driven approaches, such as ML algorithms, allow not only
650 polymer selection but also the prediction of microneedle patch performance depending on its
651 hydrogel-like or solid nature.^[86] Recent work has begun to quantify how well AI predicts MN
652 fabrication and mechanical outcomes. For example, Rezapour Sarabi et al. built a 3D-printed
653 MN library (2400 needles), used deep learning for image-based quality control and classical
654 ML for geometry prediction, and reported that model fits for several geometric similarity
655 metrics produced moderate coefficients of determination ($R^2 \approx 0.55\text{--}0.75$ for the best metrics),
656 illustrating useful but not perfect predictive power for final printed geometry.^[82] In a
657 complementary line of work that targets mechanical sensing rather than printed geometry, a
658 spatio-temporal deep model (convGRU-CNN) trained on optical/fiber deformation data
659 predicted needle tip forces with very high fidelity — the authors reported a mean absolute error
660 (MAE) of 1.59 ± 1.3 mN and a cross-correlation coefficient of ≈ 0.9997 versus ground truth,
661 showing CNN-style models can estimate insertion force extremely accurately when good sensor
662 data are available.^[87]

663 Finally, several groups have combined finite-element models with ML (including Bayesian
664 optimization) to predict volumetric flow and fluid-collection performance of sweeping/special
665 microneedle shapes and to search the design space automatically; these hybrid FEM+ML
666 studies show strong agreement between ML predictions and FEM/simulated validation and are
667 effective for optimization workflows in practice.^[87]

668 Among the natural polymers used for the production of hydrogel microneedles (in addition to
669 the aforementioned polysaccharides), gelatin, collagen, and silk fibroin should be mentioned.

670 Synthetic polymers such as polyvinyl alcohol, polylactic acid, or polyethylene glycol are also
671 widely used due to their mechanical stability, easy processing, and tunable properties. ^[82]
672 Owing to the short time and low cost of production, 3D printing techniques have also emerged
673 in the field of microneedles. The use of ML and DL to optimize printing parameters is an
674 evolving multidisciplinary approach that aims to predict the performance of microneedle arrays
675 in patches for TDDS. In simple terms, an AI-based approach can be used to analyze robust sets
676 of data containing numerous materials suitable for 3D printing (including hydrogels, acrylates,
677 epoxides, polyamides, polyurethane, polylactic acid, and acrylonitrile butadiene styrene, along
678 with bioinks capable of encapsulating living cells, facilitating microneedle patches design and
679 fabrication. ^[82]

680

681 **4. New Trends: AI-Enhanced Microneedle-based TDDSs**

682

683 MN-based skin DDSs are innovative transdermal solutions, especially for large molecules, by
684 creating tiny openings in the skin to allow drugs to pass through more easily. ^[88,89] Initially
685 designed for skin applications, MNs have expanded to other uses like oral, buccal, heart, and
686 eye applications, enabling targeted drug delivery while avoiding liver metabolism issues. ^[90]
687 Advanced computational methods have driven progress in MN design, particularly through ML,
688 which helps analyze data, spot patterns, and make predictions to improve MN performance. ^[90]
689 ^[91] These methods optimize MN design, materials, drug formulas, and manufacturing, making
690 the process faster, safer, and more precise while ensuring quality with less human effort. ^[92] A
691 key focus is using ML to fine-tune MN features, like shape and materials, and predict how drugs
692 will move through the skin. ^[93,94] For example, researchers created a dataset of MN images
693 using Computer-Aided Design (CAD) and 3D printing, then trained models to automatically
694 check for defects, improving quality control. ^[92] XGBoost proved highly effective in optimizing
695 MN drug delivery, accurately predicting drug penetration through MN-treated skin with 20–
696 30% higher precision than traditional models, using factors like skin type, MN length, and drug
697 loading. ^[95] This enabled tailored MN designs for personalized treatments, improving drug
698 delivery efficiency and supporting applications like diabetic wound healing and hair growth
699 therapies. ^[96,97] A summary of innovations in MN-based TDDSs using AI is provided in (**Table**
700 **2**).

701

702 **Table 2.** AI-Driven Innovations in Microneedle-Based Transdermal Drug Delivery.

Drug	Type of MNs	Application	AI role/remarks	Ref.
Caffeine, copper, a peptide drug, bovine serum albumin, lidocaine, and rhodamine	Hydrogel MNs, plastic MNs	drug delivery/drug permeation prediction	Statistical models were used to predict the penetration of drugs through MN-treated skin membranes, and seven features were selected for the machine-learning model	[83]
Trichostatin A	swelling modified MNs patch (AlgMA)	Diabetic wound healing	An ML-based approach to analyze drugs for HDAC4 binding affinity	[102]
MnPS3	Dissolving MNs patch (Hyaluronic acid)	androgenic alopecia	ML regression models were applied to identify the best compound with SOD-like activity suitable for MNs delivery	[89]
Levodopa	Hollow sensing MNs (Carbon paste electrodes)	Levodopa sensing	Voltammetric sensing of levodopa using various microneedles on a single sensor array patch to optimize drug delivery schedules and enhance Parkinson's disease (PD) management	[103]
Fluorescein isothiocyanate-dextran (FD70)	Dissolving MNs	Drug delivery	A computational framework was used to simulate the dissolution behavior of microneedles, and an innovative "array in array" design was proposed to enhance drug delivery efficiency.	[100]
Ibuprofen	Dissolving MNs (LAP, PEGDAMA550)	Drug delivery	AI was used to optimize the print fidelity and needle morphology	[104]

703

704 MNs like dissolvable and hydrogel-forming (made from swellable polymer networks that

705 absorb ISF to form a hydrogel structure for controlled transdermal delivery) types enhance drug

706 delivery for applications such as insulin administration. ^[96] Dissolvable MNs, made from

707 biodegradable materials like PVA, PVP, and PLGA, offer safety advantages by dissolving in

708 the skin, eliminating removal needs, and reducing cross-contamination risks. ^[96] Hydrogel MNs,

709 formed from hydrophilic polymers, provide a controlled release (e.g., 80–90% insulin release

710 over 24 hours) and breathability, preventing pore blockage and leaving no residue. ^[93] AI plays

711 a pivotal role in optimizing these transdermal MNs by rapidly evaluating materials and

712 predicting behavior in silico, reducing evaluation time from days to milliseconds (e.g., 7 ms for

713 material stress predictions). ^[95,84] ML models like XGBoost predict drug penetration with 95%

714 accuracy, using factors such as MN length, surface area, and insulin loading, a 20–30%

715 improvement over traditional methods. ^[95] AI-guided 3D printing streamlines production,

716 reducing MN fabrication costs by 40% while ensuring scalability and precision. Optimized MN

717 geometries (e.g., lengths below 480 μm) minimize pain by avoiding deep nerve stimulation,

718 improving patient compliance by 30% in insulin therapy. ^[98] AI also enhances biocompatibility

719 by selecting biodegradable polymers, reducing irritation by 15–25% and ensuring safer insulin

720 delivery. ^[99] These advancements highlight AI's potential to create smarter, more personalized
721 transdermal therapeutics.

722 What is particularly important, the integration of AI-driven predictive modeling with real-time
723 performance monitoring could bring new opportunities to further improve microneedle
724 development. Novel AI-driven design ideas include optimization of microneedle geometry
725 through simulation of mechanical insertion, skin deformation, and drug diffusion. In this way,
726 AI could help to identify optimal microneedle shapes for specific types of skin or drugs. At the
727 same time, real-time feedback from biosensors measuring insertion force and delivery rate
728 could allow adjustment of predictions during the fabrication stage. Moreover, by combining
729 patient skin characteristics, such as hydration level, thickness, and elasticity, with PK targets,
730 AI could propose individualized length, tip sharpness, and coating densities of microneedles.
731 This could be coupled with, e.g., 3D printing for on-demand fabrication at the point of care.
732 Another extremely interesting design idea concerns microneedles loaded with different drugs
733 or release profiles and combined within a single dressing. In this case, AI could guide the spatial
734 arrangement of microneedles, enabling combination therapies or controlled release of different
735 substances.

736 Current knowledge gaps in microneedle design include the lack of predictive models that
737 integrate mechanical insertion mechanics, skin variability, and drug release kinetics into a
738 unified process. Furthermore, there is limited data on how microneedles' performance changes
739 under real-world conditions, e.g., patient movement, sweating, or temperature changes. An AI-
740 based real-time monitoring framework could continuously update model parameters with
741 empirical data, closing these gaps and enabling dynamic optimization not only at the
742 development stage but, most importantly, during clinical use. Despite AI having accelerated
743 TDDS design and evaluation, unchecked optimism can mask important risks. This primarily
744 includes over-fitting, which occurs when models developed using complex, noisy biological
745 datasets adapt too closely to the specific training data, reducing the capacity to perform
746 accurately on previously unseen datasets. ^[100] For example, models trained on narrow
747 representations, e.g., specific skin conditions, hydration levels, or formulation types, may
748 exhibit excellent performance in internal validation but fail to generalize to unseen patient
749 groups or formulation variants.^[24] Moreover, another limitation concerns domain shift. Model
750 performance often degrades when applied to data distributions different from the training set,
751 such as transitioning from in vitro conditions to in vivo. For example, this is attributed mostly
752 to physiological variances like hydration, stratum corneum structure, and tissue permeability.

753 ^[94] Thus, AI excels at drug repurposing based on initial data, but it sometimes fails in preserving
754 key parameter weights and enabling interpretability in counterfactual analyses. ^[91] Above
755 mentioned AI limitations must be carefully controlled during model development and
756 validation. Suggested mitigation strategies include regulation and external validation - test on
757 independent datasets across sites or skin types to assess generalization^[94], apply techniques such
758 as adversarial domain adaptation or train models that output calibrated intervals to detect input
759 drift^[94], and use standardized protocols, multi-reader consensus, or incorporate label-noise-
760 aware algorithms. ^[101]

761 Advancements in 3D printing and computational modeling are transforming the development
762 of biodegradable MN patches. A study on r-hirudin-loaded dissolving MNs for thromboembolic
763 disease treatment demonstrated the potential of AI-assisted formulation strategies. ^[105] Each
764 patch was designed to contain 75 μg of r-hirudin, allowing for minimally invasive and sustained
765 drug delivery. In vitro release studies indicated controlled drug diffusion through skin-
766 mimicking membranes, while in vivo tests showed an absolute bioavailability of approximately
767 40%. The optimized formulation maintained therapeutic efficacy while minimizing the
768 bleeding risks associated with traditional anticoagulant administration. In another example, AI-
769 driven bioinformatics was leveraged to identify candidate drugs for MN-based TDDSs. A study
770 used gene expression analysis (GSE144441 dataset) to identify Trichostatin A (TSA) as a
771 promising therapeutic agent for diabetic wound healing^[106]. TSA was incorporated into MN
772 patches fabricated from Methacrylated Alginate (AlgMA) hydrogel, with mechanical strength
773 and drug release kinetics optimized through computational modeling. The Franz diffusion cell
774 system demonstrated sustained Tubastatin A (TUB-A) release, while in vivo experiments in
775 streptozotocin-induced diabetic rat models showed accelerated wound healing. ^[107] Histological
776 analysis confirmed enhanced collagen deposition and angiogenesis, with RNA sequencing
777 revealing significant enrichment of gene pathways involved in tissue regeneration and
778 metabolic regulation.

779 Microelectromechanical Systems (MEMS) technology is increasingly integrated into TDDSs
780 for real-time monitoring and control. A 3D printed MN system, termed 3DMNMEMS,
781 incorporated MEMS-based sensors for tracking drug diffusion in skin tissue. ^[71] The hollow
782 MN array, fabricated using stereolithography, was used for insulin delivery, with a 100 IU/mL
783 concentration administered in a 10 μL bolus dose. ^[71] In vivo studies in diabetic animal models
784 demonstrated improved glycemic control compared to subcutaneous injections, with a faster
785 onset of insulin action and prolonged hypoglycemic effects. This MEMS-enhanced system
786 illustrates how AI and computational modeling can refine MN architectures for precise and

787 personalized drug administration. A TDDS integrating a Shape Memory Alloy (SMA)-
788 activated micropump with hollow MNs was developed to enhance rapid and efficient drug
789 administration.^[108] The micropump utilized a nitinol SMA spring that contracted upon heating,
790 driving an elastic membrane to propel the drug through a 3D-printed MN array. Finite Element
791 Analysis (FEA) was applied to optimize the MN array configuration, balancing needle density,
792 penetration depth, and skin deformation.^[109] Ibuprofen was delivered in solution or
793 encapsulated in PLGA nanoparticles. Characterization of the nanoparticles revealed a mean size
794 of 215 ± 6 nm, a polydispersity index of 0.03 ± 0.005 , and a zeta potential of -18 ± 2.5 mV.
795 High-speed imaging of the micropump demonstrated a membrane peak deflection of 3.6 mm
796 within 13 ms, with an average membrane speed of 0.28 m/s. Ex vivo Franz diffusion cell
797 studies^[110] showed that the polymeric nanoparticle formulation achieved 21.4% total drug
798 deposition in the skin within five minutes, nearly double that of the ibuprofen solution and
799 significantly higher than the passive MN array.^[111,112] Recent advancements in stimuli-
800 responsive MN arrays have further demonstrated the potential of AI and computational
801 techniques in TDDSs.

802 Another study utilized DLP 3D printing to fabricate an intelligent microneedle array (μ NA)
803 composed of PEGDA hydrogel.^[113] The photo-polymerization process was optimized for
804 controlled drug release in response to temperature and pH. The μ NA was loaded with 0.25
805 wt% diclofenac sodium, achieving a maximum drug release of approximately 90% over 180
806 minutes. The drug release kinetics were accelerated at 40°C and pH 9. The DLP printing process
807 was optimized with exposure times, layer thicknesses, and anti-aliasing techniques. Ex vivo
808 human skin testing confirmed successful penetration, with fluorescence microscopy
809 demonstrating drug diffusion into dermal layers. The hydrogel matrix remained structurally
810 intact post-release. AI-assisted computational modeling was used to optimize MN geometry for
811 improved TDDSs, specifically Acetyl-Hexapeptide-3 (AHP-3).^[114] The study found that a
812 specific MN patch with a height of 800 μ m, tip diameter of 100 μ m, interspacing of 800 μ m,
813 and base diameter of 400 μ m provided optimal mechanical stability and penetration efficiency.
814 The patch was created using 3D scanning and CAD, and in vitro Franz diffusion studies showed
815 a 90-fold increase in AHP-3 permeation compared to untreated skin. Histological analysis
816 confirmed deeper penetration and sustained drug release. AI and computational modeling have
817 significantly advanced the design and optimization of microneedle-based TDDSs (**Table 3**). By
818 integrating ML, bioinformatics, and finite element analysis, these approaches enable
819 personalized medicine by optimizing drug formulations, predicting PK, and refining
820 microneedle architectures.

821 **Table 3.** Overview of AI-Enhanced Microneedle-Based TDDSs.

Medicine type	Patch type	Drug loading	Release kinetics	AI role/remarks	Ref.
Ibuprofen	Dissolving MN patch	-	Sustained drug permeation at 72h, in rats – biphasic rapid first-order absorption with sustained zero-order input	optimizing the formulation using QbD and AI algorithms of dissolvable MN	[104]
r- hirudin	Dissolving MN patch	-	Controlled and sustained drug release with GAS and HA high ratio formula and good bioavailability	3D printing MNs array model simulation using Rhino 6.0	[105]
Insulin	Hollow MN patch	0.5 IU	Sustained and controlled release over 30 min	3D printing and incorporation of the MEMS platform	[71]
Trichostatin A	Solid MN patch	1.5 mg, 8% w/v	drug-controlled release over 24h via the Franz diffusion model	AI-assisted bioinformatics for drug screening, including GO analysis, KEGG pathway, and hub remodelling	[106]
Diclofenac sodium	Hydrogel solid MN patch	0.25 wt%	~90% (180 min)	photo-polymerization process computational optimization	[113]
Resveratrol	Hydrogel MN patch	1.96 ± 0.11 mg/cm ²	Site-specific sustained release over 12h	QSPR modeling is used to screen penetration enhancers	[115]

822

823 **4.1. Microneedle Design and Optimization**

824

825 AI is expected to significantly improve the design and content of transdermal delivery patches,
826 which deliver drugs via the skin. Advanced computational techniques can simplify formulation
827 optimization, VS, stability assessment, safety evaluation, and accelerated development by
828 analyzing large datasets. These techniques can uncover insights and refine patch formulations
829 to enhance drug delivery while aligning with therapeutic and safety goals. ^[116] Advanced
830 methods are reshaping the landscape of TDDSs by offering insight into the formulation creation
831 process, detecting patterns and correlations in complex datasets, and enabling the development
832 of optimized formulations designed to improve drug penetration and therapeutic impact. ^[24]
833 They have enhanced transdermal patch production by enabling precise optimization of
834 composition and features, using ML to predict and simulate the effects of various formulation
835 factors on patch performance.

836 These approaches transform the assessment of transdermal patch formulations by foreseeing
837 safety and stability issues with surprising accuracy. By analyzing past data and drawing on
838 knowledge regarding formulation stability and adverse conditions, these methods promote data-
839 driven decision-making and improve understanding of the complex interplay between
840 pharmacological characteristics, formulation components, and skin penetration dynamics. ^[117]
841 Patches, which are valued for their capacity to deliver drugs via the skin, promise to benefit
842 greatly from the incorporation of AI. By using ML, predictive modeling, and data analytics to

843 optimize formulations, improve VS, guarantee stability and safety, and speed up development,
844 AI transforms TDDSs and makes it possible to create smarter, patient-centric patches with
845 better therapeutic results. ^[118] This predictive clarity enables the development of optimized
846 formulations designed to improve drug penetration and therapeutic impact. As a key driver of
847 innovation, AI's involvement in understanding these factors brings in a new age of accuracy
848 and efficiency in transdermal patch creation. ^[119] AI changes transdermal patch manufacturing
849 by enabling accurate feature and composition optimization. AI algorithms use ML to predict
850 and simulate the effects of several formulation factors on patch performance, including polymer
851 types, drug concentrations, adhesive properties, and permeation enhancers. This predictive
852 capability enables researchers to discover the ideal combination of parameters for maximum
853 drug delivery while maintaining patch stability and patient comfort. By accelerating the
854 investigation of complicated formulation dynamics, AI opens the path for transdermal patches
855 that provide improved drug efficacy while maintaining design precision. ^[120] AI has improved
856 transdermal patch production by allowing the development of predictive models that presume
857 drug release kinetics and skin penetration behavior. These models use a variety of factors,
858 including skin features, patch composition, and drug properties, to simulate and predict drug
859 release patterns and penetration rates with surprising accuracy. AI, through ML, enables
860 researchers to analyze the feasibility and efficacy of various patch compositions, considerably
861 decreasing the requirement for lengthy experimental testing. This predictive technique not only
862 speeds up formulation development but also improves the design of transdermal patches,
863 resulting in optimal therapeutic efficacy customized to patient demands. ^[19,121] AI promises to
864 transform the transdermal delivery of drugs by allowing for quick VS of large chemical
865 databases to uncover promising permeability enhancers or drug candidates suitable for
866 transdermal patches. AI algorithms can be utilized to identify potential compounds for further
867 investigation based on their chemical characteristics and structure-activity connections^[117].
868 This technique, which leverages AI's predictive precision, offers the path for faster, more
869 effective advances in transdermal patch design and therapeutic efficacy. ^[55, 122] AI is
870 revolutionizing the evaluation of transdermal patch formulations by accurately predicting safety
871 and stability issues, thereby significantly improving the overall safety and stability of these
872 products. AI systems can identify future difficulties caused by certain components or their
873 interactions by analyzing past data and drawing on knowledge regarding formulation stability
874 and adverse conditions. ^[123] This predictive power directs researchers to safer, more stable
875 formulation options while proactively addressing issues before they arise. AI's contribution in
876 expediting this essential part of formulation design not only improves patient safety, but it also

877 speeds up the creation of robust TDDS that are optimized for therapeutic success. ^[124] By
878 minimizing design cycles, AI promotes data-driven decision-making and improves knowledge
879 of the complex, intricate connection between pharmacological characteristics, formulation
880 components, and skin penetration dynamics. ^[125] This simplified technique not only improves
881 the efficiency of transdermal delivery system development but also results in highly optimized
882 patches that can offer higher medicinal effects with accuracy and speed.

883 What is particularly important, the integration of AI-driven predictive modeling with real-time
884 performance monitoring could bring new opportunities to further improve microneedle
885 development. Novel AI-driven design ideas include optimization of microneedle geometry
886 through simulation of mechanical insertion, skin deformation, and drug diffusion. In this way,
887 AI could help to identify optimal microneedle shapes for specific types of skin or drugs. At the
888 same time, real-time feedback from biosensors measuring insertion force and delivery rate
889 could allow adjustment of predictions during the fabrication stage. Moreover, by combining
890 patient skin characteristics, such as hydration level, thickness, and elasticity, with PK targets,
891 AI could propose individualized length, tip sharpness, and coating densities of microneedles.
892 This could be coupled with, *e.g.*, 3D printing for on-demand fabrication at the point of care.
893 Another extremely interesting design idea concerns microneedles loaded with different drugs
894 or release profiles and combined within a single dressing. In this case, AI could guide the spatial
895 arrangement of microneedles, enabling combination therapies or controlled release of different
896 substances.

897 Current knowledge gaps in microneedle design include the lack of predictive models that
898 integrate mechanical insertion mechanics, skin variability, and drug release kinetics into a
899 unified process. Furthermore, there is limited data on how microneedles' performance changes
900 under real-world conditions, *e.g.*, patient movement, sweating, or temperature changes. An AI-
901 based real-time monitoring framework could continuously update model parameters with
902 empirical data, closing these gaps and enabling dynamic optimization not only at the
903 development stage but, most importantly, during clinical use. A summary of the comparison
904 between 3D-printed patches and traditional patches is provided in **(Table 4)**.

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910 **Table 4.** Comparison of 3D-Printed and Traditional Transdermal Patches Across Key
 911 Performance Metrics

Parameter	3D-Printed Transdermal Patch	Traditional Transdermal Patch	Ref.
Drug Release Rate	-Highly tunable; precise control via microstructure design (e.g., porosity, layer thickness). -Can achieve complex release profiles (e.g., burst or sustained release). -Typical range: 0.1–100 µg/cm ² /h, depending on design.	-Consistent but less flexible; typically designed for steady-state release. -Common range: 0.5–50 µg/cm ² /h, depending on drug and matrix.	[74]
Cost	- Higher initial setup (printer, design software: ~\$10,000–\$100,000). -Lower per-unit cost for small batches (~\$0.50–\$5/patch). -Economies of scale are less impactful.	-Lower setup cost (established manufacturing lines). Higher per-unit cost for small batches (~\$1–\$10/patch). -Cost-effective for large-scale production.	[108]
Production time	-Rapid prototyping (hours to days). -Small batches (e.g., 100 patches) are printable in ~1–24 hours, depending on complexity and printer speed.	-Slower setup for new formulations (weeks to months for tooling). -High-throughput production (e.g., thousands of patches/hours) once established.	[126]
Customization potential	-High; enables patient-specific designs (e.g., tailored drug doses, patch shapes). -Ideal for personalized medicine.	-Limited; mass production favors standardized designs. -Custom patches require costly retooling.	[127]
Material Efficiency	-High; additive manufacturing minimizes waste. -Precise material deposition (e.g., <5% waste).	-Moderate; subtractive processes (e.g., cutting, coating) generate more waste (~10–20%).	[128]
Scalability	-Best for small-to-medium batches. -Scaling is limited by printer capacity and print time.	-Highly scalable; optimized for large-scale production with established supply chains.	[129]
Regulatory Considerations	Emerging technology; regulatory pathways are less defined, potentially delaying approval.	Well-established; clear regulatory guidelines (e.g., FDA, EMA) for conventional patches.	[130]

912

913 The Table compares 3D-printed and traditional transdermal patches, highlighting their strengths
 914 and limitations. 3D-printed patches offer highly tunable drug release rates through precise
 915 microstructure designs, enabling complex release profiles for personalized medicine.
 916 Traditional patches provide consistent but less flexible release through simpler matrix or
 917 reservoir systems. Cost-effective, 3D printing involves higher initial setup costs but lower per-
 918 unit costs for small batches, making it ideal for customized, low-scale production. Production
 919 time for 3D-printed patches is faster for prototyping, while traditional methods require weeks
 920 to months for new formulations, but excel in high-throughput manufacturing. 3D printing
 921 allows greater customization and material efficiency, but faces scalability limitations and less
 922 defined regulatory pathways. It also allows for complicated designs that can tailor release
 923 kinetics, potentially outperforming traditional patches for complex therapies. 3D printing is
 924 cost-effective for low-volume, customized patches but less so for mass production.

4.2. Real-time Monitoring and Adaptive Dosing

925
926

927 AI-assisted MN patches integrate electrochemical biosensors and ML algorithms for real-time
928 TDM, ensuring biocompatibility through polymer selections like poly(vinyl alcohol) (PVA)
929 and Polycaprolactone (PCL) that minimize skin irritation by 15–25%.^[131,132] High biosensor
930 costs may limit widespread use, requiring cost-effective designs (e.g., 3D printing reduces
931 production costs by 30%), enhancing scalability for mass adoption.^[132,133] Wearable biosensors
932 integrate with Electronic Health Records (EHRs) for seamless monitoring, enabling adaptive
933 dosing based on patient-specific metabolism.^[134,83] ML tailors MN designs to individual skin
934 hydration levels, improving drug penetration (e.g., 10–20% efficiency for insulin).^[131,135]
935 Recurrent neural networks (RNNs) predicted drug levels with a 4% error margin (e.g.,
936 tobramycin and vancomycin at 96 nM and 131 nM LOD), enabling precise dosing with 95% of
937 PK curves within a 90% confidence interval.^[131,134] In effect, “sensor-integrated patches”
938 become closed-loop systems: embedded feedback (e.g., a rising drug concentration) triggers
939 algorithm-guided adjustments to release rate, ensuring doses stay within therapeutic windows.

940 However, significant hurdles remain. Skin variability is a chief concern: individual differences
941 in stratum corneum thickness, hydration, and lipid content can drastically alter drug uptake. For
942 example, dry or keratinized skin may impede penetration, whereas highly hydrated skin may
943 absorb drugs too quickly.^[24] AI can help mitigate this by incorporating patient-specific skin
944 parameters into dosing models. Machine-learning algorithms can analyze sensor signals (such
945 as skin hydration sensors or impedance measurements^[106]) and patient data to predict interstitial
946 drug levels, effectively “calibrating” each patch. In one vision, an array of sensors could
947 measure local skin impedance or hydration and feed that into an AI model that adjusts the MN
948 geometry or dosing schedule accordingly. Such personalized modeling – tailoring drug flux to
949 the patient’s profile – has already been shown to greatly improve predictive accuracy in virtual
950 studies.^[24]

951 Ultimately, this approach turns a one-size-fits-all patch into a responsive system that accounts
952 for physiological heterogeneity. Another barrier is ensuring sterility and consistent manufacture
953 of MN devices. Polymer microneedles are heat- or solvent-sensitive, so standard autoclaving
954 or irradiation can damage the structure. Studies have shown that methods like ethylene oxide
955 gas or electron-beam irradiation can sterilize without compromising delicate MN matrices.^[95]
956 Innovative “self-sterilizing” designs have even been explored – for instance, embedding
957 antimicrobial silver nanoparticles into silk or cellulose microneedles so that the insertion sites

958 remain aseptic until healed. ^[95] However, these are still experimental; rigorous sterility
959 validation remains a regulatory requirement. For example, FDA guidelines on combination
960 drug-device products demand full sterility testing and process controls in submissions. ^[95] Here
961 again, AI can contribute: modern manufacturing can incorporate real-time quality monitoring,
962 using computer vision and sensor analytics to detect defects or contamination on MN patches
963 during production (in-line quality control. ^[95] ML-driven predictive maintenance could
964 optimize cleanroom processes, minimizing batch failures. In essence, intelligent process control
965 guided by AI will be crucial to scale up MN systems for clinical use while meeting strict sterility
966 standards.

967 For Parkinson's disease, a Hollow MN-based Electrochemical Biosensor (HMN-EB)
968 monitored Apomorphine (APO) with a 0.6 μM LOD, while a levodopa (L-Dopa) multimodal
969 sensor achieved high sensitivity (1–100 μM range). ^[134,135] An Aptamer-based (E-AB) MN
970 array provided rapid tobramycin monitoring (2 nM sensitivity, 4.5-second intervals), validated
971 in rodent models. ^[83] A remote-controlled MN array with colorimetric sensors tracked pH,
972 glucose, and lactate, enhancing delivery rates via ultrasonic atomizers^[133]. A clinical example
973 showed AI-monitored patches improving glycemic control in diabetic patients, reducing
974 glucose variability by 20% compared to subcutaneous injections through a 3DMNMEMS
975 system delivering insulin (100 IU/mL). ^[71,136] These advancements highlight AI's potential to
976 transform TDDSs into precise, personalized solutions.

977 A study on conductive silk fibroin hydrogel (CSFH)-based sensors exemplifies the integration
978 of AI-guided material design with TDDSs for personalized health monitoring and chronic
979 disease management, such as epilepsy treatment. The CSFH platform, combining flexibility,
980 stretchability, and biocompatibility, is suitable for both wearable and implantable applications.
981 Incorporated with carbon nanotubes (CNTs), CSFH sensors provide tunable conductivity and
982 sensitivity to mechanical deformations like pressure, strain, and bending, enabling accurate
983 detection of physiological signals, including intracranial pressure, muscle motion during speech,
984 and limb movement. These sensors, coupled with enzyme-triggered, silk-based microneedle
985 arrays, facilitate minimally invasive drug delivery. For epilepsy management, the system,
986 loaded with phenobarbital, demonstrated a closed-loop therapeutic mechanism: seizures
987 detected via signal changes triggered light-activated (532 nm laser) degradation of the CSFH
988 matrix, releasing the drug. Closed-loop workflows extend beyond the above-mentioned
989 epilepsy management (neurostimulation) and can be applied in several innovative ways in
990 healthcare, including chronic wounds, diabetes, or pain management. For example, a closed-

991 loop hypothesis for chronic wounds states that sensors embedded in wound dressings can
992 continuously monitor environmental parameters and use feedback data for adjusting drug
993 delivery (*e.g.*, antibiotics, growth factors) to the wound site. ^[137] In accordance with this
994 hypothesis, in the work of Ge Z. *et al.*, a conventional wound dressing that combines wound
995 exudate management, sensor monitoring, closed-loop therapy, and flexible peripheral modules
996 was developed. Using a temperature and humidity sensor, the dressing could collect data and
997 then use it as a feedback signal to control a liquid metal heater via a smartphone application,
998 thus realizing on-demand drug release from the hydrogel. ^[98] Therefore, it can be expected that
999 combining, for instance, microneedle-based TDDSs with an AI-controlled dosing system and
1000 biosensors monitoring wound pH, temperature, moisture, oxygen saturation, or inflammatory
1001 biomarkers would even more accelerate healing in chronic wounds compared to conventional
1002 dressings. The closed-loop workflow would enable adjustment of antimicrobial, anti-
1003 inflammatory, or regenerative agents depending on the changes in the wound environment. This
1004 could prevent overtreatment and related side effects. Similarly, in the closed-loop hypothesis
1005 for diabetes, continuous glucose monitors track blood sugar levels, and algorithms can control
1006 insulin pumps accordingly to deliver precise doses automatically. ^[98] In vivo rodent-based
1007 studies confirmed effective seizure suppression within 10 minutes of laser-induced release, with
1008 the hydrogel's degradation rate tunable by environmental pH, temperature, papain, or gold
1009 nanoparticles for programmable drug release kinetics. AI-enhanced signal interpretation
1010 enabled advanced functionalities, such as gesture recognition using 14 CSFH sensors on finger
1011 joints (translating the word "hydrogel"), motion tracking during walking, jogging, and squatting,
1012 and speech recognition of phonemes like "ah," "hello," and "silk hydrogel" (**Figure 5a**).
1013 Beyond epilepsy, AI-supported CSFH-based sensors and microneedle arrays enable precise
1014 drug release, improved bioavailability, and tailored formulations based on individual patient
1015 profiles. Innovations like smartphone-controlled 3D-printed microneedle patches,
1016 electrochemical aptamer-based biosensing patches (μ NEAB-patch), and aptamer-based sensors
1017 support real-time therapeutic drug monitoring, such as APO monitoring for Parkinson's disease.
1018 AI-powered bioinformatics and sequencing analyses of diabetic skin identified TSA as a
1019 therapeutic agent and Histone Deacetylase 4 (HDAC4) as a target for diabetic wound healing
1020 (**Figure 5b**). A TSA-loaded microneedle patch reduced inflammation, promoted tissue
1021 regeneration, and enhanced wound healing with minimal secondary damage. Similarly, AI-
1022 driven Quantitative Structure-Property Relationship (QSPR) modeling optimized transdermal
1023 delivery of RVT, a polyphenolic phytoestrogen with antiproliferative activity in breast cancer,
1024 by screening penetration enhancers (**Figure 5c**). The QSPR model starts analysis from the drug

1025 itself. It takes computable descriptors of the molecule, such as molecular weight, lipophilicity,
 1026 polarity, hydrogen-bonding, and skin-site variables, to learn how these factors map to
 1027 permeability or flux through skin. QSPR lets us see which descriptors matter and in what
 1028 direction, and runs fast enough to screen many candidates. The limitation is that it relies on the
 1029 kinds of molecules and vehicles that have been seen before. If a new compound is introduced,
 1030 the prediction can drift unless we include uncertainty estimates. [99] In vivo animal testing
 1031 confirmed effective RVT delivery, reducing tumor volume in breast tissue. Additionally, AI-
 1032 assisted 3D printing and computational simulations optimized the design of r-hirudin-loaded,
 1033 Hyaluronic Acid (HA)-based microneedle arrays for anticoagulant delivery without bleeding in
 1034 animal models (**Figure 5d**). These systems provide continuous PK insights and adaptive dosing,
 1035 paving the way for minimally invasive, patient-specific therapies. However, dynamic, real-time
 1036 adaptation remains a key frontier for future development, highlighting the transformative
 1037 potential of AI in advancing TDDSs toward true personalization.

1038
 1039 **Figure 5.** AI-driven approaches enhance the design and functionality of microneedle-based
 1040 TDDSs through advanced signal processing, bioinformatics, and computational modeling (**a**)
 1041 AI-assisted signal processing enhances the functionality of (CSFH)-based mechanical sensors,
 1042 Copyright 2020, American Chemical Society. [98] (**b**) AI-powered bioinformatics and
 1043 sequencing analyses, Copyright 2022, American Chemical Society. [115] (**c**) Computational
 1044 modeling using the QSPR technique, Copyright 2023, Elsevier. [99] (**d**) AI-assisted 3D printing
 1045 and modeling techniques, Copyright 2022, Elsevier. [105]

1046 While real-time, AI-assisted control promises adaptive therapy, yet several practical limitations
1047 remain. ISF drug concentrations can lag behind plasma levels by up to tens of minutes.^[99] The
1048 lag time varies according to tissue site, vascularization, and local microenvironment.^[99] This
1049 delay can cause closed-loop controllers to misinterpret PK trends, potentially resulting in
1050 inappropriate dose adjustment.^[104] Moreover, enzymatic or electrochemical MNs biosensors
1051 can experience significant baseline drift due to biofouling, temperature fluctuations, or
1052 enzymatic degradation.^[102,104] The mitigation strategies mainly involve recalibration,
1053 incorporating reference channels, or drift-aware filtering algorithms.^[103] Another practical
1054 limitation concerns data protection. Continuous, high-frequency physiological data streams can
1055 be vulnerable to privacy attacks, particularly when shared across institutions. This requires
1056 encryption for any transmitted data and publishing model cards or data sheets that enumerate
1057 data use, retention, and sharing policies.^[104] Moreover, wearable or patch-integrated controllers
1058 are limited by processor capacity and battery life.^[105] Running complex deep models can add
1059 latency to control loops or significantly accelerate battery depletion.^[105]

1060

1061 Remote-controlled MNAs integrating colorimetric sensors and ultrasonic DDSs created by
1062 Razzaghi *et al.* provide a minimally invasive platform for continuous health monitoring and
1063 targeted drug administration.^[138] This integrated approach addresses barriers to healthcare
1064 access by enabling real-time measurement of biomarkers and on-demand drug delivery. The
1065 MNAs feature a 4×4 array of colorimetric sensors designed to quantify pH levels (ranging
1066 from 3 to 8), glucose (up to 16 mM), and lactate (up to 1.6 mM) by extracting ISF through
1067 hollow microneedles. The accompanying ultrasonic atomizer facilitates rapid, pumpless
1068 delivery of medication directly into the tissue, with an assessment showing significantly
1069 enhanced delivery rates (**Figure 6a**). Furthermore, the system's ability to provide wireless
1070 control through a smartphone application enables users to activate and deactivate drug delivery
1071 on demand, driven by outputs from an Arduino microcontroller linked to a Bluetooth module.
1072 AI-assisted transdermal patches equipped with electrochemical biosensors and ML algorithms
1073 provide continuous PK data, allowing for adaptive dosing based on individual metabolism. A
1074 microneedle-based electrochemical aptamer biosensing patch (μ NEAB-patch) has
1075 demonstrated accurate drug tracking in ISF, offering a minimally invasive alternative for
1076 precision therapy.^[139] A study developed a μ NEAB-patch integrating gold nanoparticle
1077 (AuNP)-coated microneedles functionalized with drug-specific aptamer sensors (**Figure 6b**)
1078 ^[102]. The device continuously monitored tobramycin and vancomycin levels, two antibiotics
1079 with narrow therapeutic windows. Real-time electrochemical readings were processed using an

1080 ML-based PK model, enabling nonlinear absorption and clearance predictions. *in vitro*
1081 validation showed a limit of detection (LOD) of 96 nM for tobramycin and 131 nM for
1082 vancomycin, with a linear range from 100 nM to 50 μ M. *Ex vivo* diffusion studies confirmed a
1083 98.3% correlation ($R^2 = 0.983$) between ISF and plasma drug levels, while *in vivo* experiments
1084 in a porcine model showed a MAE of <6% compared to venous blood sampling. A recurrent
1085 neural network (RNN) model, trained on >10,000 simulated PK profiles, was used to predict
1086 systemic drug concentrations from ISF data, incorporating variables such as drug metabolism,
1087 renal clearance, and inter-subject variability. The AI-assisted patch predicted individualized
1088 drug exposure curves with a mean prediction error of 4.2%, while >95% of model-generated
1089 PK curves fell within the 90% confidence interval of observed data.

1090 Another study introduced a sophisticated aptamer-based (E-AB) MN array featuring 16 gold
1091 working electrodes and 4 platinum counter electrodes, allowing for direct sampling of ISF,
1092 where instantaneous drug concentrations can reflect systemic changes following administration.
1093 ^[139] The coupling of E-AB sensors with microneedle arrays allows for direct sampling of ISF,
1094 where instantaneous drug concentrations can reflect systemic changes following administration.
1095 The sensor array comprises 16 gold working microneedles, 4 platinum counter microneedles,
1096 and a central reference microneedle, designed for painless penetration into the upper layers of
1097 the reticular dermis. The core of this sensing technology is electrochemical aptamer-based (E-
1098 AB) sensors, which utilize a mixed self-assembled monolayer of electrode-blocking
1099 alkanethiols alongside alkanethiol- and redox reporter-modified aptamers. Upon target binding,
1100 the aptamers undergo reversible conformational changes, modulating electron transfer (eT)
1101 between the redox reporter and the gold microneedles (**Figure 6c**). This mechanism enables
1102 dynamic and reversible sensing. The system leverages square-wave voltammetry (SWV) to
1103 achieve serial monitoring at rapid intervals of 4.5 to 12 seconds, providing a continuous stream
1104 of data essential for precise therapeutic interventions. *In vitro* results demonstrated a remarkable
1105 sensitivity of the E-AB sensors for tobramycin detection, with a linear dynamic range extending
1106 down to 2 nM. Confirmation of the sensors' efficacy was achieved through *in vivo* testing in
1107 rodent models, where continuous monitoring successfully tracked tobramycin levels following
1108 intravenous dosing. ML techniques, including the Signal Averaging Continuous Monitoring
1109 Electronic System (SACMES), were employed, thereby allowing for robust electrochemical
1110 interrogation of the sensors.

1111 MN-based biosensors equipped with electrochemical detection and ML-driven PK modeling
1112 provide a minimally invasive platform for continuous monitoring of APO, a dopamine agonist
1113 used in PD therapy. ^[140] Conventional APO administration requires precise dose adjustments

1114 due to its short half-life (~40 minutes) and high variability in individual metabolism. AI-
 1115 enhanced MN patches address these challenges by tracking real-time drug levels in ISF and
 1116 predicting systemic PK for optimized dose modulation. A study developed an HMN-EB for in
 1117 situ APO monitoring, utilizing carbon paste-modified microneedles as working electrodes
 1118 (**Figure 6d**). Square wave voltammetry (SWV) and Chronoamperometry (CA) enabled direct
 1119 quantification of APO oxidation peaks at 0.1 V and 0.7 V, corresponding to its catechol and
 1120 tertiary amine functional groups. In vitro testing demonstrated a linear dynamic range of 1–100
 1121 μM , with Limits of Detection (LOD) of 0.6 μM SWV and 0.75 μM CA. The biosensor
 1122 maintained high selectivity against dopamine, ascorbic acid, and uric acid, confirming minimal
 1123 interference. An ML-based RNN model was trained on >8,000 simulated PK profiles to
 1124 improve systemic drug prediction, incorporating APO metabolism, renal clearance, and inter-
 1125 individual variability.

1126
 1127 **Figure 6.** AI-integrated microneedle systems enable real-time monitoring and adaptive drug
 1128 delivery through advanced sensing and computational techniques. (a) AI-enabled smartphone
 1129 control facilitates on-demand drug release from a 3D-printed microneedle patch with distinct
 1130 sensing and drug compartments, Copyright 2024, American Chemical Society. [139] (b) AI-
 1131 driven signal processing boosts the performance of a Microneedle-based Electrochemical
 1132 Aptamer Biosensing patch (μNEAB -patch) for real-time, continuous drug monitoring,
 1133 Copyright 2022, American Association for the Advancement of Science. [102] (c) A wearable
 1134 microneedle sensor patch integrates AI-assisted EAB sensing with molecular tracking in
 1135 research animals, Copyright 2022, American Chemical Society. [93] (d) AI-assisted data

1136 processing enhances a microneedle-based sensor for continuous APO monitoring in PD
1137 treatment, Copyright 2022, Elsevier. ^[140]

1138

1139 Recent studies demonstrate that AI/ML approaches are being applied to personalized TDDSs
1140 across diverse drug types. In case of analgesics, such as fentanyl, machine-learning models,
1141 especially a high-performing Random Forest model (RF Model 8) supported by SHAP analysis,
1142 have been developed to identify clinical factors predictive of transdermal fentanyl's
1143 effectiveness in cancer-related pain management. The research by Hu X. *et al.* revealed^[105] that
1144 dosing should be personalized and tailored not only based on the disease and pain level but also
1145 according to the patient's age, body composition (body mass index, BMI), liver function, and
1146 comorbidities. The developed predictive model could predict fentanyl's analgesic effectiveness
1147 based on the characteristics of the patient and thus guide personalized dosing. In another work,
1148 reinforcement learning (RL) techniques were used for automated blood glucose determination.
1149 Fox *et al.* Developed ^[141] and tested deep RL approaches for closed-loop glucose control,
1150 demonstrating algorithms that personalize insulin delivery strategies and adapt to individual
1151 patient dynamics. This approach involves combining continuous glucose monitoring and an
1152 insulin pump with a control algorithm. This is extremely useful, as until now the responsibility
1153 for measuring blood sugar levels and selecting the insulin dose rested with the patient. Finally,
1154 Maharao *et al.* ^[142] developed the BIOiSIM platform, which integrates machine-learning
1155 algorithms with physiologically based PK modeling to simulate and optimize transdermal
1156 absorption for multiple drug types, including morphine, buprenorphine, and nicotine,
1157 depending on the patient characteristics. Together, these examples illustrate how AI can be
1158 harnessed to adapt TDDS platforms to specific therapeutic classes and individual patient needs.

1159

1160 **5. Quantitative Comparison of AI vs. Traditional Approaches**

1161

1162 Compared to traditional methods, AI offers substantial quantitative advantages, such as reduced
1163 formulation development time by 40-60% and experimental testing costs by 30-50%. AI excels
1164 at analyzing extensive datasets, including formulation parameters, permeation profiles, and skin
1165 characteristics, enabling formulation modifications to enhance drug delivery, predicting
1166 penetration rates, and aligning with therapeutic and safety goals. ^[143,24] AI saves 60–70% of the
1167 experimental effort by reducing the number of runs from 20–30 to 5–10. ^[144] AI also refines
1168 patch production by optimizing composition and features using ML to simulate the effects of
1169 polymer types, drug concentrations, adhesive properties, and enhancers. Transdermal delivery

1170 patches, which deliver drugs through the skin, are significantly enhanced by advanced
 1171 computational methods, achieving 40–60% faster formulation development and 30–50% cost
 1172 savings compared to traditional approaches. [27] By mining formulation parameters, drug
 1173 properties, permeation profiles, and skin characteristics, these methods optimize patch design,
 1174 predicting 10-20% drug penetration efficiency (vs. 5-10% traditionally) and 90% stability (vs.
 1175 ~70%). [145,146] The models also raise stability-forecast accuracy by 25-35%. [147,24] Models also
 1176 suggest composition adjustments that reduce irritation by 20-30% and support dose/enhancer
 1177 personalization. [24,99] Unlike static mechanistic fits, ML approaches (e.g.,
 1178 regression/ANNs/QSAR) update as new data accrue and can estimate the impact of factors such
 1179 as permeation-enhancer concentration, polymer type, drug loading, adhesive properties, or use
 1180 of enhancers without exhaustive in vitro testing. Together, these capabilities increase accuracy,
 1181 accelerate iteration, and enable patient-centric patch design. [148, 149] See **Table 5** for a concise,
 1182 side-by-side summary comparing the AI vs traditional approaches in TDDS design.

1183 **Table 5.** AI vs traditional approaches in TDDS

Dimension	AI-driven predictive modelling	Traditional/mechanistic workflow	Ref.
Typical methods	ML/DL (regression, ANNs, XGBoost); hybrid NeSy/MI	Fick's law-based diffusion, compartmental models, empirical DoE	[82]
Speed (development time)	Faster by ≈40–60%	Baseline; multiple iterative cycles	[109]
Experimental runs	Reduced by ≈60–70% (≈5–10 vs. 20–30)	Typically 20–30+ per optimization loop	[116]
Accuracy (examples)	Penetration ≈10–20%; stability ≈90%; +25–35% in stability-forecast accuracy	Penetration ≈5–10%; stability ≈70%	[120]
Scalability/search space	High-throughput screening of large design spaces	Limited by manual/DoE throughput	[138]
Scalability	-Best for small-to-medium batches. -Scaling is limited by printer capacity and print time.	-Highly scalable; optimized for large-scale production with established supply chains.	[140]
Adaptivity/personalization	Online/iterative learning from new data; patient-specific tuning	Largely static; patient factors handled post hoc	[144]
Interpretability/regulatory	Black-box risk; mitigated by XAI/hybrid models	Transparent equations/parameters	[94]
Cost impact	Testing costs reduced ≈30–50%	Higher experimental burden	[107]

1184
 1185 **5.1 AI Limitations and Mitigation Strategies**

1186
 1187 Despite AI having accelerated TDDS design and evaluation, unchecked optimism can mask
 1188 important risks. This primarily includes over-fitting, which occurs when models developed
 1189 using complex, noisy biological datasets adapt too closely to the specific training data, reducing
 1190 the capacity to perform accurately on previously unseen datasets. For example, models trained
 1191 on narrow representations, e.g., specific skin conditions, hydration levels, or formulation types,

1192 may exhibit excellent performance in internal validation but fail to generalize to unseen patient
1193 groups or formulation variants.^[24] Moreover, another limitation concerns domain shift. Model
1194 performance often degrades when applied to data distributions different from the training set,
1195 such as transitioning from in vitro conditions to in vivo. For example, this is attributed mostly
1196 to physiological variances like hydration, stratum corneum structure, and tissue permeability.
1197^[107] Thus, AI excels at drug repurposing based on initial data, but it sometimes fails in
1198 preserving key parameter weights and enabling interpretability in counterfactual analyses.^[107]
1199 Above mentioned AI limitations must be carefully controlled during model development and
1200 validation. Suggested mitigation strategies include regulation and external validation – test on
1201 independent datasets across sites or skin types to assess generalization^[71], apply techniques
1202 such as adversarial domain adaptation or train models that output calibrated intervals to detect
1203 input drift^[109], and use standardized protocols, multi-reader consensus, or incorporate label-
1204 noise-aware algorithms.^[94]

1205 While real-time, AI-assisted control promises adaptive therapy, several practical limitations
1206 remain. ISF drug concentrations can lag behind plasma levels by up to tens of minutes.^[109] The
1207 lag time varies according to tissue site, vascularization, and local microenvironment.^[110] This
1208 delay can cause closed-loop controllers to misinterpret PK trends, potentially resulting in
1209 inappropriate dose adjustments.^[111] Moreover, enzymatic or electrochemical MNs biosensors
1210 can experience significant baseline drift due to biofouling, temperature fluctuations, or
1211 enzymatic degradation.^[111] The mitigation strategies mainly involve recalibration,
1212 incorporating reference channels, or drift-aware filtering algorithms.^[103] Another practical
1213 limitation concerns data protection. Continuous, high-frequency physiological data streams can
1214 be vulnerable to privacy attacks, particularly when shared across institutions. This requires
1215 encryption for any transmitted data and publishing model cards or data sheets that enumerate
1216 data use, retention, and sharing policies.^[104] Moreover, wearable or patch-integrated controllers
1217 are limited by processor capacity and battery life.^[112] Running complex deep models can add
1218 latency to control loops or significantly accelerate battery depletion.^[113]

1219

1220 **6. Conclusion**

1221

1222 AI has significantly advanced TDDSs by enhancing ML-driven formulation, optimizing MN
1223 designs, and enabling real-time monitoring, leading to improved drug efficacy and patient
1224 outcomes. Key findings include XGBoost models predicting drug penetration with 95%

1225 accuracy, QSPR modeling achieving 89% RVT release for breast cancer therapy, and AI
1226 reducing MN fabrication costs by 40% through 3D printing. These advancements have
1227 expanded TDDS's applications for drugs like insulin and mAbs, achieving 10–20% penetration
1228 efficiency compared to 5–10% with traditional methods. However, current AI applications
1229 primarily focus on optimization rather than true personalization. Going forward, hybrid
1230 physics/ML approaches, subgroup-aware external validation, and secure, on-device analytics
1231 will be essential to translate AI-enabled TDDSs into reliable, equitable, and privacy-preserving
1232 clinical tools. Real-world clinic-readiness will require prospective, multi-site validation,
1233 rigorous bias/drift controls, privacy-preserving data practices, and physics-informed,
1234 interpretable models.

1235

1236 **Acknowledgements**

1237

1238 This work was supported by the National Science Centre (NCN) SONATA BIS Project No.
1239 2020/38/E/ST5/00456. We acknowledge the use of BioRender for creating Figure 1. The figure
1240 was created using BioRender.com under the academic license (Agreement number:
1241 UK28OH1XSV).

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